

R CURVE BEHAVIORS IN WHISKER REINFORCED CERAMICS

Y. Kagawa, M. Enoki, K. Ikeda and T. Kishi
(The University of Tokyo, Tokyo 153, Japan)

ABSTRACT

Crack growth behaviors of an SiC whisker reinforced borosilicate glass matrix model composite have been investigated using DCB specimen. R curve of the composite was obtained and the R curve behavior was discussed with possible toughening mechanisms. Experimental results showed that the unique R curve behavior appeared and the curve was considered due to toughening mechanisms at zone wake. After K_R reached steady state, repeated increase/decrease K_R behavior appeared. This behavior was due to macroscale crack deflection.

INTRODUCTION

It has been well known phenomenon that addition of whisker to brittle materials enhances fracture toughness of those monolithic materials. The toughening behavior of the ceramics matrix composite materials is closely related to the failure process and the crack growth resistance. So far whisker reinforced glass materials, recent studies revealed that the fracture behavior of whisker reinforced glass composites often exhibited macroscale non-linear stress-strain response [1,2] and this behavior was explained by microscale failure behavior during the failure process of composites [3,4]. Mechanical properties of the composite were often influenced with microscale failure behaviors [5,6] and macroscale crack growth resistance curve [7].

However, details of crack growth phenomena in whisker reinforced glass matrix composites are not clearly understood. Our attention has been focused on the failure behavior and the crack growth phenomena of whisker reinforced glass matrix composites. This paper summarizes our recent experimental results on the crack growth behavior in whisker reinforced glass matrix composites.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

SiC whisker reinforced borosilicate glass matrix composite, whose volume fraction was 0.2, was used as a model material. The SiC whiskers used in that experiment were single crystal of α -SiC and were obtained from Tateho Chemical Co. Ltd., Japan. The producer's technical data shows average diameter of the whisker varied from 0.05 to 0.2 μm and length from 10 to 40 μm . The Young's modulus and tensile strength of the SiC whiskers were

estimated at 490 GPa and 2.1 GPa, respectively. The Corning Glass Works borosilicate glass powders 7740 were used as starting glass powder matrix.

The SiC whiskers and glass powders mixture was prepared using a conventional dry processing technique. The mixture was hot-pressed in high purity nitrogen gas atmosphere at the temperature of 1100 K under the pressure of 10 MPa for 30 min. Details of processing condition and problems were already reported [8]. The SiC whiskers were nearly three-dimensionally random-oriented in the borosilicate glass matrix. The density of the composite was 99.8 % of the theoretical value calculated from the density of the raw materials.

As hot-pressed composite discs were mechanically cut into double cantilever beam (DCB) specimen as shown in Fig. 1. A guide groove was introduced along one side of the specimen. The DCB specimens were pre-notched to various lengths with a 200 μm thick cutting blade. The notch width and root radius were 210 μm and 105 μm , respectively.

A crack gauge, with grid spacing was 1.0 mm, was adhered to the smooth side of the specimen to enable to record load against crack growth length. The reinforcing effect of the adhesive was checked before the experiment and was found negligibly small.

The mechanical tests were run using an Instron-type universal testing machine with a stiff pin loading adjustment that allows slow crack growth. Load-loading point displacements were recorded at constant crosshead speed of 8.33×10^{-7} m/s and 1.67×10^{-6} m/s. All experiments were performed at room temperature (293 K) in air. Five specimen were tested for the each condition.

After the test, the fracture appearances and surfaces were observed by optical microscope and scanning electron microscope, respectively, to determine fracture morphology of the composite.

RESULTS

Figure 2 shows a typical load-loading point displacement curve of the SiC whisker reinforced borosilicate glass matrix composite specimen. The curve exhibited characteristic four distinct stages (Stage I to IV). At stage I, the composite deforms wholly elastically without any crack extension. However, at stage II, nonlinearity appeared and the load approached to the maximum load with a little saw-toothed behavior. In this stage, growth of microcracks from a root of notch was observed just prior to the maximum load. After stage II, load decreased with increasing loading point displacement. The load drop in this stage was not monotonous and the load drop accompanied some noticeable cusps. This characteristic stage was represented as stage III. Stage IV was a final stage of the load-displacement curve. In stage IV, crack propagated rapidly and, finally, specimen was completely separated into two pieces. The macroscale crack propagation velocity at stage III was very low, and therefore, failure behavior in this stage was considered stable crack propagation stage. These failure behaviors of the composite were independent of the crosshead speeds.

Figure 3 shows typical crack resistance (K_R) curve of the

SiC whisker reinforced borosilicate glass matrix composite obtained from stages II and III. The value of stress intensity factor K_R was calculated from the analysis of Freiman et al [9]. The calculated K_R data were plotted against the actual crack growth length from a notch root.

The K_R curve behavior of the composite was that the R-curve extends for about 15 mm (cut off crack length a_c) of the crack extension before reaching with the constant value. This R curve behavior of the composite was independent of the crosshead speeds. The fracture toughness value (K_R) increased from $K_R = 3.0 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ at $a = 0$ up to $4.2 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ at $a = 15 \text{ mm}$. The steady state, K_R was about $4 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$ and was 5 times larger than that obtained from the unreinforced borosilicate glass ($K_{IC} = 0.8-0.9 \text{ MPa m}^{1/2}$) [4,6].

However, detail of the K_R curve was not so smooth as the conventional ceramics materials. After crack length reached a_c , the K_R curve exhibited repeated increase and decrease of K_R with increased crack growth length. This unique repeated R curve behavior is essentially the same as the recently reported paper [10].

Macroscopic fracture behavior of the SiC whisker reinforced borosilicate glass matrix composite is shown in Figure 4. The macroscopic crack path in the composite was irregular and this result suggested that the main crack was deflected macroscopically during the crack propagation. Figure 5 shows detail of crack deflection observed at the point of crack length longer than the cutoff crack length ($a > a_c$).

Typical fracture surfaces of the composite at the stable crack growth region are shown in Fig. 6. As clearly seen in these photographs, microscale crack deflection of the composite by the SiC whiskers, microcrack formation in the matrix and/or whisker-matrix interfaces, and pulled-out of whiskers was clearly recognized. Some holes, of which diameter was approximately the same as the whisker diameters, were considered memory of pulled out whiskers.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

Crack propagation resistance of the SiC whisker reinforced borosilicate glass composites ($V_f=0.2$) has been obtained using the DCB specimen. The crack growth resistance was discussed in terms of R curve behavior. The R curve behavior, K_R versus a , of the composite had following features.

1) K_R increased with natural crack length increasing; the relation between K_R and crack length follows as:

$$\begin{aligned} K_R &= q(a-a_0)^n, & n \approx 0.5 & & a \leq a_c \\ K_R &= \text{const.} \pm \Delta K_R & & & a > a_c \end{aligned}$$

where q is constant and a_0 is initial crack length, and a_c is cut off crack length, ΔK_R is the amplitude of increase/decrease of K_R .

2) Increase of K_R with crack length was principally due to whisker bridging and pullout at zone wake. Microscale crack deflection [11] also enhanced fracture toughness, however, this

mechanism seems to be independent of crack length a .

3) Repeated increase/decrease of K_R curve during the steady state ($a > a_c$) was due to large scale crack deflection. In this region, macroscale toughening mechanisms, including microscale crack deflection, were superimposed on the large scale crack deflection.

Detail quantitative analyses should be required to understand R curve behavior of whisker reinforced composites. However, our simple theoretical model [12] and model experiments in short carbon fiber reinforced glass ceramics [13] revealed that the crack bridging and pullout behaving a crack tip should play very important role in the R curve behavior of the short fiber reinforced ceramics.

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